

The Case of RedressHub: An LLM-Assisted Relation Extraction Pipeline for Mapping Colonial Redress Initiatives in Belgium

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RedressHub¹ is an online platform that maps initiatives addressing and redressing colonial harms and their enduring legacies in Belgium. Although often framed as a closed historical era, colonialism continues to shape present-day societies through structural injustices and systemic inequalities. In response, a growing range of institutional and civil-society actors have launched measures such as policy reforms, truth-seeking processes, apologies, restitution, memorialisation, and the removal of colonial symbols. A comprehensive, accessible and cross-sectoral overview of these myriad initiatives, however, has been missing, limiting opportunities for awareness raising, coordinated action and shared learning.

RedressHub seeks to address this gap by offering an interactive, multilingual, and cross-sector data platform for identifying and analysing redress efforts. Its map-based interface integrates geospatial and time-series visualisations with advanced search and filter functions. It is built in NodeGoat as a relational database (Bree van P. & Kessels G., 2013). A key challenge is that, while abundant information on redress initiatives is available across different digital sources and legacy and social media, manually mapping this information for populating the database is extremely labour-intensive and no off-the-shelf technological solution exists for automated information retrieval within this specialised domain.

The sheer quantity of texts, compounded by the variety of sources and the multilingual national space of Belgium warrants the creation of an automated event extraction pipeline. Event extraction (EE) requires recognising relevant events, identifying actors, and structuring information about timelines, locations, and participants (Simon et al., 2024). While traditional EE pipelines rely on a set of sequential subtasks (trigger detection, argument classification, relation assignment), large language models (LLMs) enable broader narrative and document-level reasoning across languages, and are particularly suited for joint extraction tasks and

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contextual understanding. These models can infer implicit meaning, process long documents, and capture “complex events” that span sentences or paragraphs—capabilities that are crucial when dealing with nuanced, indirect, or partially specified redress initiatives in the multilingual context of colonial redress (Hu & Li, 2024; Karjus, 2024; Tanev et al., 2025).

However, applying generative AI to this historically and politically sensitive domain requires careful oversight. Generative LLMs may hallucinate, require substantial computational resources, be difficult to evaluate, and reflect biases in their training data (Bail, 2024; Ma et al., 2025). Additionally, proprietary models such as GPT or Claude, whilst powerful, lack transparency and raise concerns for activist organisations particularly wary of big-tech infrastructures - reinforcing the broader insight that LLMs can never be blindly trusted for domain-specific inference. Despite these challenges, recent work shows that GenAI performs strongly when combined with continued expert supervision (Andersen et al., 2025; Chun & Elkins, 2023; Karjus, 2024; Ma et al., 2025). For this reason, our technical work is closely interwoven with a co-creation track that engages redress practitioners through consultations, workshops, and ethics discussions, ensuring that decisions about how data is collected and interpreted remain transparent and community-driven (Pallí-Asperó et al., 2025).

Methodology

Practical notes

Our methodology is being implemented by a team consisting of two experts in colonial redress, a digital humanist and an NLP developer. As a project management tool, a shared Notion² instance is used to keep track of experiments, discussions and to host our annotation guidelines. The annotations were made in a Label Studio instance hosted on a university server. In later steps, the computational GPU-resources of the Flemish Supercomputer (VSC) will likely be used for fine-tuning.

Data collection

Our two dedicated domain researchers first curated a collection of online sources—news outlets, event platforms, CSO websites, institutional repositories, and government portals—across Dutch, French, and English which regularly publish information relevant to redress initiatives. Examples include the website of MO³, the Belgian Africa Museum⁴ and CEC⁵ and were subsequently scraped as shown in *Table*

² <https://www.notion.com/>

³ <https://www.mo.be/>

⁴ <https://www.africamuseum.be/fr>

⁵ <https://www.cec-ong.org/>

1. Important to note is that for each of these sources, explicit permission was requested and granted by the respective organisations.

Table 1: Statistical overview of the scraped source material.

Dataset	# articles	Avg. length	Min-Max length	Languages
MO	52.265	5680	213 - 607,013	Dutch (99.6%) and French (0.4%)
AfricaMuseum	41	1920	604 - 5,317	French (97.6%) and Dutch (2.4%)
CEC	44	2733	233 - 15,493	French (100%)

Semantic relevance filter

Relevant paragraphs related to colonial redress events were filtered from the text using the multilingual-e5-base⁶ text embeddings (Wang et al., 2024). Texts were given a relevance score on the paragraph-level, and article-level threshold relevance values are currently being tuned through empirical evaluation by our domain experts.

Annotation

Domain-specific annotation framework guidelines were drafted and iteratively improved through the calculation of inter-annotator agreement and avid discussion - striking the balance between technical feasibility and usefulness of the end result to the domain expert. In our final paper, we will also focus on the development of the final annotation model in a multidisciplinary team.

Eventually, we agreed upon a relational event extraction model and annotation strategy in Figure 1 - including a range of core EVENT types, related to their respective ORGANISATION, LOCATION and TIME variables. Following the event extraction paradigm, events were annotated according to trigger words – treating the organisation, location and time as linked arguments.

As depicted in Table 2, 30 texts across the languages English, French and Dutch were annotated as a gold standard evaluation set by the domain experts and the trained digital humanist, and collectively deemed sufficient in this complex domain to

⁶ intfloat/multilingual-e5-base on HuggingFace

proceed. Currently, a dataset of 120 texts stratified across languages, sources and text lengths are being annotated as a training dataset.

Figure 1: Overview of the inter-annotator agreement of 30 texts (10/language) calculated using pairwise F1 and IoU > 0.3 across languages.

Figure 2: overview of the relational model for colonial redress event extraction. Entities include a range of EVENT types (apologies, compensation and resource provision, litigation, ...), TIME, ORGANISATION and LOCATION.

Modelling and database integration

After finishing the annotation phase – we aim to fine-tune models from the model family Qwen3 - chosen for its competitive results, non-proprietary nature under an

Apache 2.0. license, and remarkable multilingual support (119 languages and dialects) (Yang et al., 2025). Currently, we are considering instruction tuning of Qwen3.5-35B-A3B⁷ using LoRa for computational efficiency; and comparing these results to a zero-shot baseline and dynamic few-shot methodology. In a final stage, we consider using the free tool Splink to perform probabilistic record linkage (entity resolution) before delivering our data to the domain experts (Linacre et al., 2022). Eventually, the data will be manually verified and integrated in a relational NodeGoat database.

Table 2: Mock data overview of the expected results of our event extraction pipeline before probabilistic record linkage (entity resolution) with Splink.

Article	Source	Event	Time	Organisations	Location	Trigger words
<i>Article_text_0</i>	MO	Restitution	5/01/2011	<i>Jean Redress</i>	Null	Motie
<i>Article_text_1</i>	CEC	Apology	3/03/2010	<i>Koning Filip, Belgisch parlement</i>	Brussel	Excuses
<i>Article_text_1</i>	CEC	Book	3/03/2010	<i>David Reybrouck</i>	Brussel	Congo: een geschiedenis

Expected contributions

1. A reusable multilingual, expert-in-the-loop pipeline for extracting colonial redress events in French, Dutch, and English, released via GitHub and the CLARIAH Tool Hub. Models are strictly open-weights, and public compute resources are used through the Flemish Supercomputer (VSC).
2. A publicly available, multilingual annotated dataset of colonial redress events.
3. A NodeGoat-based interactive database, visualising redress initiatives in Belgium through geospatial, network, and time-series tools with accessible filtering options.

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⁷ Qwen/Qwen3.5-35B-A3B on HuggingFace

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